

The applied mastery model.

Apply this onto whatever model you want to build and / or create.

If objectively the same then specify a unit, if old positive value then specify a unit, if beginning myth of insert model name here then specify a unit.

- If objectively the same then specify a unit, if left handedness then specify a unit, if old positive value then specify a unit, if memory then specify a unit, if deciding with intention then specify a unit, if free will then specify a unit, if inserting a generalisation here then specify a unit, if inserting a specialisation here then specify a unit, if inserting a thing here then specify a unit, if in here then specify a unit, if starting then specify a unit, if press then specify a unit, if space then specify a unit, if smoke coordinate then specify a unit, if inserting a dimension here then specify a unit – if objectively the same then specify a unit, if old positive value then specify a unit, if entanglement here then specify a unit, if inserting link here then specify a unit – if objectively the same then specify a unit, if right handedness then specify a unit, if old positive value then specify a unit, if imagination then specify a unit, if deciding with intention then specify a unit, if free will then specify a unit, if inserting generalisation here then specify a unit, if inserting a specialisation here then specify a unit, if inserting thing here then specify a unit, if beginning then specify a unit, if turnover then specify a unit, if freedom then specify a unit, if time then specify a unit, if smoke coordinate then specify a unit, if inserting a dimension here then specify a unit.
- If objectively the same then specify a unit, if left handedness then specify a unit, if old positive value then specify a unit, if information then specify a unit, if deciding with intention then specify a unit, if free will then specify a unit, if inserting a generalisation here then specify a unit, if inserting a specialisation here then specify a unit, if inserting a thing here then specify a unit, if on here then specify a unit, if position here then specify a unit, if date here then specify a unit, if space then specify a unit, if particle then specify a unit, if inserting a dimension here then specify a unit – if objectively the same then specify a unit, if old positive value then specify a unit, if entanglement here then specify a unit, if inserting link here then specify a unit – if objectively the same then specify a unit, if right handedness then specify a unit, if old positive value then specify a unit, if communication then specify a unit, if deciding with intention then specify a unit, if free will then specify a unit, if inserting generalisation here then specify a unit, if inserting a specialisation here then specify a unit, if inserting thing here then specify a unit, if future then specify a unit, if moment then specify a unit, if currency then specify a unit, if time then specify a unit, if particle then specify a unit, if inserting a dimension here then specify a unit.

- If objectively the same then specify a unit, if left handedness then specify a unit, if old positive value then specify a unit, if recognition then specify a unit, if deciding with intention then specify a unit, if free will then specify a unit, if inserting a generalisation here then specify a unit, if inserting a specialisation here then specify a unit, if inserting thing here then specify a unit, if forward then specify a unit, if length then specify a unit, if day then specify a unit, if space then specify a unit, if string then specify a unit, if inserting dimension here then specify a unit - if objectively the same then specify a unit, if old positive value then specify a unit, if entanglement here then specify a unit, if inserting link here then specify a unit - if objectively the same then specify a unit, if right handedness then specify a unit, if old positive value then specify a unit, if perception then specify a unit, if deciding with intention then specify a unit, if free will then specify a unit, if inserting generalisation here then specify a unit, if inserting a specialisation here then specify a unit, if inserting thing here then specify a unit, if future then specify a unit, if curved then specify a unit, if distance then specify a unit, if second then specify a unit, if time then specify a unit, if string then specify a unit, if inserting a dimension here then specify a unit.
- If objectively the same then specify a unit, if left handedness then specify a unit, if old positive value then specify a unit, if sense then specify a unit, if deciding with intention then specify a unit, if free will then specify a unit, if inserting a generalisation here then specify a unit, if inserting a specialisation here then specify a unit, if inserting thing here then specify a unit, if right then specify a unit, if area then specify a unit, if month then specify a unit, if space then specify a unit, if wave then specify a unit, if inserting dimension here then specify a unit - if objectively the same then specify a unit, if old positive value then specify a unit, if entanglement here then specify a unit, if inserting link here then specify a unit - if objectively the same then specify a unit, if right handedness then specify a unit, if old positive value then specify a unit, if identification then specify a unit, if deciding with intention then specify a unit, if free will then specify a unit, if inserting generalisation here then specify a unit, if inserting a specialisation here then specify a unit, if inserting thing here then specify a unit, if acute then specify a unit, if angle then specify a unit, if minute then specify a unit, if time then specify a unit, if wave then specify a unit, if inserting dimension here then specify a unit.
- If objectively the same then specify a unit, if left handedness then specify a unit, if old positive value then specify a unit, if knowing then specify a unit, if deciding with intention then specify a unit, if free will then specify a unit, if inserting a generalisation here then specify a unit, if inserting a specialisation here then specify a unit, if inserting thing here then specify a unit, if up then specify a unit, if volume then specify a unit, if year then specify a unit, if space then specify a unit, if field then specify a unit, if inserting dimension here then specify a unit - if

objectively the same then specify a unit, if old positive value then specify a unit, if entanglement here then specify a unit, if inserting link here then specify a unit - If objectively the same then specify a unit, if left handedness then specify a unit, if old positive value then specify a unit, if understanding then specify a unit, if deciding with intention then specify a unit, if free will then specify a unit, if inserting a generalisation here then specify a unit, if inserting a specialisation here then specify a unit, if inserting a thing here then specify a unit, if rotation then specify a unit, if degree then specify a unit, if hour then specify a unit, if time then specify a unit, if field then specify a unit, if inserting dimension here then specify a unit.

- Insert hidden and / or seen variables specified above, if question then specify a unit, if wall then specify a unit, if decade then specify a unit, if above then specify a unit, if topout then specify a unit, if orb then specify a unit – if objectively the same then specify a unit, if old positive value then specify a unit, if entanglement here then specify a unit, if inserting link here then specify a unit – insert hidden and / or seen variables specified above, if answer then specify a unit, if layer then specify a unit, if covered then specify a unit, if cycle then specify a unit, if orb then specify a unit.
- Insert hidden and / or seen variables specified above above the paragraph, if assumption then specify a unit, if membrane then specify a unit, if century then specify a unit, if out then specify a unit, if climb then specify a unit, if tower then specify a unit, if land then specify a unit – if objectively the same then specify a unit, if old positive value then specify a unit, if entanglement here then specify a unit, if inserting link here then specify a unit – insert hidden and / or seen variables specified above above, if suggestion then specify a unit, if portal then specify a unit, if gap then specify a unit, if through then specify a unit, if around then specify a unit, if bridge then specify a unit, if zone then specify a unit.

If objectively the same then specify a unit, if old positive value then specify a unit, if middle myth of insert model name here then specify a unit. If objectively the same then specify a unit, if old positive value then specify a unit, if ending myth of insert model name here then specify a unit.

Note: There is a left handedness space linked with a right handedness time model, and a left handedness time linked with a right handedness space model. Another question arises is that of what do I mean by saying the dimensions? Usually it means just the XYZ coordinate system, with the time coordinate added onto it as the 4th dimension, here is actually a list of what I mean by inserting a dimension here:

- The seen nothing winner dimension.
- The hidden something winner dimension.
- The seen 1st winner dimension.

- The hidden 2nd winner dimension.
- The seen 3rd winner dimension.
- The hidden inner dimension.
- The seen inner dimension.
- The hidden middle dimension.
- The seen middle dimension.
- The hidden outer dimension.
- The seen outer dimension.
- The hidden last dimension.
- The seen last dimension.
- The hidden final dimension.
- The last hidden winner dimension.
- The seen winner something last dimension.
- The hidden winner nothing last dimension.

Another note, this model shifts around and variables that have places are free to move around the model selection process in any, all, and every way possible. There is also a 14 lettered alphabet axis that this model shifts around on as well.

To save me the hassle, I proceed to simplify a model where people are free to apply the mastery model onto it, where it goes like this:

The beginning myth of the haze model.

Bulb position space entangled with light moment time. Beam length space entangled with ray distance time. Radiance area space entangled with glow angle time. Shining volume space entangled with sunny moment time.

Another note is that for a subjective model, subjectivity is different, and for an imaginary model, is a what you want the model to exist as. And again, there are things that are objectively the same as each other, such as a glass cup is the same as another glass cup, however there may also be differences, such as that of colour, and what is contained within the cup, such as soda as compared with juice.

(IF > gate > #*THEN > open > #*THEN > shared... > then > <<<<!>?\@&*).